

ANNUAL REPORT ON MNCH INDICATOR APPLICATION 2

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Author(s)	Katharina Wieser (UGRAZ), Celeste Madondo (Wits RHI), Jaspas Maguma (CeSHHAR), Annie Portela (WHO), Debra Jackson (LSHTM), Nina Gerlach (WHO), Ilona Otto (UGRAZ)
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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
CCHI	Climate Change and Health Indicator
CeSHHAR	Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (Zimbabwe)
CHAT	Child Health Accountability Tracking technical advisory group
DHB	District Health Barometer
DHS	Demographic and Health Survey
EU	European Union
EWENE	Every Women Every Newborn Everywhere
HDC	Health Data Collaborative
HHAP	Heat and Health Action Plan
LMIC	Low- and Middle-Income Countries
LSHTM	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (United Kingdom)
MNCH	Maternal, Newborn, and Child Health
MoNITOR	Mother and Newborn Information for Tracking Outcomes and Results
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NIDS	National Indicator Dataset (South Africa)
PAHO	Pan American Health Organization
PPIP	Perinatal Problem Identification Programme (South Africa)
SES	Socio-economic status
UGRAZ	University of Graz (Austria)
UN	United Nations
UNICEF	United Nations Children's Fund
UNPFA	United Nations Population Fund
WHO	World Health Organization
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
ZICC-EH	Zimbabwe Intersectoral Coordination Cluster on Climate, Environment, and Health

Executive Summary

This report presents an overview of the current status, challenges, and progress in monitoring and applying heat-related maternal, newborn, and child health indicators. It synthesises the findings from an indicators mapping, linking the World Health Organization-HIGH Horizons conceptual framework for extreme heat and maternal, newborn, and child health to existing indicators used in global monitoring, a mapping exercise conducted to identify maternal, newborn, and child health indicators in country heat-health action plans, and insights from country-level indicator application in South Africa and Zimbabwe. Significant gaps in validated indicators are highlighted, particularly for direct health impacts and vulnerability factors, with many indicators captured mainly through research rather than routine health systems. The content analysis of national heat-health action plans shows that while children and pregnant individuals are commonly recognised as vulnerable, few plans include detailed or age-disaggregated heat-health indicators for maternal, newborn, and child health. Country-level experiences from South Africa and Zimbabwe show progress in indicator integration and multisectoral collaboration, alongside persistent challenges such as data quality issues, limited real-time reporting, funding constraints, and the need for clear health-sector definitions of heatwaves. Overall, the findings emphasise the urgent need to further develop, validate, and harmonise heat-health indicators for maternal, newborn, and child health and strengthen data systems and coordination mechanisms to enable effective monitoring. We will build on this work in the final report, which will be delivered in August 2026.

1 Introduction

This document provides an overview of recent activities related to the process of heat-related maternal, newborn and child health (MNCH) indicator application. It presents indicators used in MNCH global monitoring within the [conceptual framework on heat and MNCH](#) developed by the World Health Organization (WHO) and HIGH Horizons (WHO, 2024) as well as a summary of MNCH and heat indicators identified from a mapping exercise conducted to identify MNCH-related actions and indicators in country heat and health action plans (HHAP) (Czerniewska et al., 2025). Updates and learnings from the indicator implementation processes in South Africa and Zimbabwe, are also discussed, and work underway to capture the perspectives from stakeholders in different contexts is presented. The content of this document including the process proposed to identify indicators reflects a shift away from a top-down process, as written in previous deliverables, toward one that prioritises learning from countries and ensuring that their experiences guide the global indicator development and the subsequent uptake and use in global, regional and national policies.

The learnings, recommendations and needs that come from the indicator application in South Africa and Zimbabwe as well as an overview of indicators that are already measured either in research or in routine health information systems help to inform the selection of a final set of indicators by the WHO Expert Group (convened within the context of HIGH Horizons).

Some of the key connections to other deliverables about indicators are listed in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1. Current deliverables related to indicators

Title	Source
D2.1 Environmental and Health Databases 1	(Brimicombe, Wieser, Otto, et al., 2024)
D2.3 Heat-health analysis report from Italian, Swedish and African data 1	(Brimicombe, Wieser, Monthaler, et al., 2024)
D2.6 Updated systematic review 1	(Lakhoo et al., 2024)
D3.1 Expert Group established and operational	Available from the CORDIS website
D3.2 Selected indicators	(WHO, 2024)
D4.1 Indicator Workshop	(Brimicombe, Madondo, Portela, et al., 2024) [°]
D4.2 Annual report on MNCH indicator application 1	(Wieser et al., 2024) [°]

Note: ° These deliverables have been submitted in 2024 and are awaiting approval before publishing them publicly.

Table 2. Future deliverables related to indicators

Title	Expected date
D2.2 Environmental and Health Databases 2	August 2025
D2.4 Heat-health analysis report from Italian, Swedish and African data 2	August 2025
D2.7 Updated systematic review 2	August 2025
D2.5 Heat-health attribution report	February 2026
D4.5 Hand-over of indicators for routine use	February 2026
D5.1 Evaluation of the proposed indicators	May 2026
D4.4 Annual report on MNCH indicator application 3	August 2026
D6.4 WHO/UNICEF/UNFPA/WMO publication on global and national indicators for monitoring impact of heat on MNCH	August 2026

2 Background

The HIGH Horizons project focuses, amongst other objectives, on the selection of global heat-health indicators for monitoring the impact of heat on MNCH. The project brings together evidence from secondary data analysis described in deliverables D2.1-D2.5, findings from the systematic review updates of D2.6 and D2.7, and the mapping of content of HHAPs with learnings from country-level workshops to discuss indicators and stakeholder consultations, creating a base for identifying indicators on heat impacts on MNCH (see Figure 1).

As two national workshops were held early in the project’s timeline, these findings also feed into the decision-making process by the WHO Expert Group (see D3.1 and D3.2). This approach reverses the originally planned sequencing but aligns with a global shift towards more integrated and participatory methodologies in climate-health research contrary to a top-down approach, where indicators are first selected and then countries are consulted.

Figure 1. Indicator selection process within HIGH Horizons

Note: This diagram outlines the HIGH Horizons approach to building a knowledge base on heat-related MNCH impacts. It integrates global evidence, including systematic reviews, modelling, and indicator mapping, with country learnings from expert consensus, feasibility monitoring, workshops, and stakeholder consultations to evaluate and refine proposed indicators.

In deliverable D4.2, the annual report for indicator application 1, Wieser et al. reported on the monitoring of climate change and health indicators within Austria, Finland, Italy, South Africa, and Zimbabwe. It was found that many countries do not yet have official monitoring processes in place for climate change and health indicators and are reliant on regional or global processes such as the Lancet Countdown for Climate Change and Health (Romanello et al., 2023). In addition, most researchers were not familiar with the climate change and health indicators

(CCHI) in their countries. South Africa emerged as an exception, with a structured, stakeholder-driven process for selecting CCHIs in place (Wieser et al., 2024).

The D4.2 report pointed out some of the key findings of the first Expert Group meeting convened by WHO, including the potential of combining indicators that are already monitored for climate and health, for example, linking temperature data with data on stillbirth rates, also emphasising the need for country-level discussion (WHO 2024). A lack of coordination between the meteorological and health sectors was identified as a major barrier. Finally, the report gave an overview of CCHIs already monitored by international and national health agencies and initiatives (Wieser et al., 2024).

Since then efforts have been made to map and extend the CCHIs identified to the WHO-HIGH Horizons heat-MNCH framework, to determine their use in countries and in research and the validation status. Furthermore, a content analysis of national HHAPs was conducted, identifying existing content that relates to MNCH, including activities, indicators, and key messages (Czerniewska et al., 2025).

HIGH Horizons previously reported on discussions held in South Africa and Zimbabwe on starting a process for identifying national MNCH heat indicators that has continued (Brimicombe, Madondo, Portela, et al., 2024). Another in-country workshop on MNCH indicators is planned in Greece from 15-16 December 2025.

In this report, we aim to summarise the key insights that have come from the ongoing efforts. We begin with providing an overview of the indicators mapping, linking the WHO-HIGH Horizons conceptual framework for extreme heat and MNCH to existing indicators used in MNCH global monitoring. We then describe the process of applying indicators at the country level, with South Africa and Zimbabwe as examples, before discussing plans for consultations with additional stakeholders. By this, we aim to outline a national and sub-national perspective on measuring and implementing heat-health indicators for monitoring the impact of extreme heat on MNCH.

3 Identification of MNCH and heat indicators

Health indicators specific to heat and MNCH are essential for assessing the impacts of climate change on vulnerable populations. These indicators enable governments to track trends, inform public health interventions, allocate resources effectively, and develop evidence-based policies (Di Napoli et al., 2022). Children, the elderly, pregnant women, and individuals with pre-existing health conditions are particularly at risk from extreme heat and other climate hazards (Cele et al., 2020).

Subchapter 3.1 outlines the process of mapping indicators already identified in global MNCH monitoring systems and scientific literature to the WHO-HIGH Horizons framework categories (e.g., hazards, vulnerability factors, and direct and indirect impacts). This process helps clarify which indicators are already validated, where data can be sourced, and where gaps remain.

Subchapter 3.2 then examines how MNCH considerations are currently reflected in national and subnational HHAPs. This analysis is critical for understanding how countries are currently planning for, and monitoring, the impacts of extreme heat on MNCH populations, as well as identifying gaps in the use of age- or pregnancy-disaggregated data.

3.1 Indicators mapped to WHO-HIGH Horizons conceptual framework

[MoNITOR](#) and [CHAT](#) are technical advisory groups that support WHO (and UNICEF for CHAT) by harmonising guidance and standardising indicators to help countries effectively track health, wellbeing, and Sustainable Development Goals progress. A WHO team, supported by the HIGH Horizons team at University of Graz (UGRAZ), made efforts to map indicators identified in their conceptual framework for extreme heat and MNCH to existing indicators used in MNCH global monitoring,

reviewing the MoNITOR and CHAT databases, and all outcomes identified in the last annual report on indicator application on associations between heat exposure and maternal and neonatal health outcomes conducted by HIGH Horizons (Wieser et al., 2024). The objective was to determine the data source: research such as the Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) or other household surveys or research studies identified through the systematic reviews, versus those that are captured by routine health information systems. It was also noted whether indicators had been validated. Indicators were mapped to the areas within each category in the conceptual framework: heat hazards, vulnerability factors, direct impacts, indirect impacts, maternal health, fetal and perinatal health, newborn health, and child health and development.

Figure 2. WHO-HIGH Horizons framework on extreme heat and MNCH

Figure 2 shows the WHO-HIGH Horizons framework on extreme heat and MNCH (WHO, 2024). Areas within the framework, where at least one validated indicator is available, such as increased intensity, duration, and frequency of heat stress and heatwaves within the heat hazard category, or heat strain within the direct impacts

category, are marked in green. Areas, where the validation status is unclear, are marked in yellow (e.g., hospital admissions in the newborn health category). Areas not highlighted reflect that no validated indicator is available.

The exact number of indicators per area, as well as how many are validated, is shown in Figure 3. While most indicators relate to intermediary impacts, such as care-seeking behaviour, service delivery, quality of care, and response times, fewer indicators are available for direct health impacts. These include areas such as dehydration, endocrine system dysfunction, and the release of heat shock proteins. Similarly, there are fewer indicators covering maternal health conditions like gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, and gestational diabetes, or vulnerability-related areas such as compound hazards and biological susceptibility. While there were indicators identified related to newborn health, most of them have not been validated.

Figure 3. Number of indicators and validation status by category in the WHO-HIGH Horizons conceptual framework

Note: Indicators were identified through mapping to MNCH global monitoring indicators in the MoNITOR and CHAT databases, and outcomes from HIGH Horizons' last annual report on indicator application. Data sources include the Demographic and Health Survey (DHS), other household surveys, research studies, and routine health information systems.

Figure 4 shows how the collected indicators are measured: solely through research instruments (Research), those that are captured by routine health information systems (Routine), or by both (Both); and for some, the measurement method was unclear (Unclear).

Figure 4. Number of indicators and measurement method by category in the WHO-HIGH Horizons conceptual framework

Note: Indicators were identified through mapping to MNCH global monitoring indicators in the MoNITOR and CHAT databases, and outcomes from HIGH Horizons' last annual report on indicator application. Data sources include the Demographic and Health Survey (DHS), other household surveys, research studies, and routine health information systems.

The findings show that most indicators related to heat hazards are included in routine health information systems, but many indicators related to direct impacts and vulnerability factors are mainly identified through research studies.

3.2 Indicators identified in HHAPs

In a recent publication commissioned by WHO and involving WHO and UGRAZ, Czerniewska et al. (2025) identified national and subnational HHAPs, published between January 2004 and July 2024 through multiple search channels. The study assessed whether, and in what ways, these HHAPs include actions and indicators related to pregnant, postpartum, or breastfeeding individuals; newborns; and children. HHAPs were defined as 'a national or subnational, government-authored

plan/strategy that considered the health risks of heat and presented a comprehensive set of prospective planned or recommended actions to reduce the effect of heat on human health, or to increase resilience to heat in the population' (Czerniewska et al., 2025). In total, 83 HHAPS from 24 countries were identified, predominantly from high-income (49%) and lower-middle-income economies (47%); no HHAPs were identified from low-income countries. Most HHAPs identified children as a key population to protect (83%), and fewer (52%) mentioned pregnant individuals. Newborns (39%) or postpartum and breastfeeding individuals (14%) were less frequently mentioned. While no HHAP extensively addressed MNCH risks during extreme heat, four (5%) HHAPs included plans to collect or monitor data for health-related outcomes with disaggregation by age group. Table 3 summarises the indicators for which age-disaggregated data will be collected or monitored, indicating where the HHAP is implemented, the year of publication, and the age categories used for stratification.

Table 3. Health indicators for which age-disaggregated data collection or monitoring is planned in identified HHAPs

Location	Year	Indicator	Stratification
Vaud, Switzerland	2020	Number of visits to paediatric departments	Under / over five years of age
Portugal	2022	Total number of primary healthcare consultations	Age groups; Groups not defined
Portugal	2022	Total number of emergency hospital consultations	Age groups; Groups not defined
Madrid, Spain	2022	All-cause mortality	Age groups; Groups not defined
Spain	2023	Estimated deaths attributable to excess temperature	Age groups; Youngest group: 0-14 years

An additional 14 (17%) of HHAPs included tools indicating that age data would be collected, although they do not define indicators or their planned analysis. Two (2%) HHAPs from Bangladesh (2024) and Karachi, Pakistan (2017) briefly mention the need to collect data on the pregnancy status of people affected by heat-related illnesses or death (Czerniewska et al., 2025).

4 Application of MNCH and heat indicators

The findings from the previous chapter highlight gaps in the integration of MNCH heat-health indicators into HHAPs, revealing that many plans do not yet systematically incorporate these measures. Consequently, monitoring heat exposure and its associated health outcomes remains limited and under-researched, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). Without robust indicators, it is challenging to assess the effectiveness of adaptation strategies, track progress over time, or ensure accountability in climate and health actions. Furthermore, climate-health research and integration within the health sector remain insufficient in many settings (Chersich & Wright, 2019)

The development and application of heat-MNCH indicators not only guide practical interventions but also establish a framework for accountability, ensuring that climate action prioritises the protection of public health, especially for those most at risk. This chapter builds on the identification of indicators by describing recent developments, stakeholder involvement, challenges, and lessons learned from South Africa (Section 4.1) and Zimbabwe (Section 4.2) in the process of defining and implementing heat-MNCH indicators in real-world settings.

4.1 South Africa

The South African Heat Action Guidelines identify children, the elderly, pregnant women, and individuals with pre-existing health conditions as particularly vulnerable to the impacts of extreme heat (Cele et al., 2020). However, monitoring heat exposure and related health outcomes among these groups remains limited in the country.

Given the increasing burden of climate change and extreme weather events on South Africa's health system, integrating climate-health considerations and building a robust monitoring system are critical. Heat-MNCH indicators offer a

means to strengthen preparedness, track progress, and ensure accountability for protecting the most vulnerable populations.

4.1.1 Recent developments

➤ *Indicator review and selection for NIDS*

The timing of the heat-MNCH indicator selection and prioritisation workshop held by HIGH Horizons and national stakeholders in January 2024 was strategic. It aligned with the National Indicator Dataset (NIDS) review cycle, which occurs every three years and provides an opportunity to revise, retain, or introduce indicators. The workshop's findings and proposed heat-MNCH indicators were submitted for consideration as part of this cycle, ensuring their potential inclusion in the updated NIDS. The review process has been completed, with all previously proposed indicators retained. However, the newly suggested indicator on preterm birth was not approved for inclusion. Instead, the National Health Technical Committee recommended that the maternal health programme revives and strengthens support for the Perinatal Problem Identification Programme (PPIP).

➤ *District Health Barometer*

The District Health Barometer (DHB) is a key statistical and analytical resource that offers a comprehensive overview of district-level performance on essential health systems indicators in South Africa. It provides in-depth analysis of trends, challenges, and progress across districts, enabling managers and stakeholders to identify priorities, plan targeted interventions, and monitor outcomes (Ndlovu et al., 2025). The 17th edition of the DHB includes for the first time a dedicated chapter on the health impacts of climate change in South Africa. A team from HIGH Horizons partner Wits RHI authored and contributed to this chapter, highlighting the growing challenges faced by the health sector and advocating for proactive preparations to address climate-related impacts. In particular, the team emphasised the urgent need to establish indicators that can monitor, measure, and help mitigate these adverse effects.

➤ *Sharing lessons*

A key highlight was presenting the process followed to select heat-MNCH indicators for tracking in South Africa. This was shared during a webinar convened by the National Department of Health through the Knowledge Hub platform, which drew over 3,000 virtual participants. Additionally, key considerations for implementing indicator monitoring, particularly within a One Health framework, were shared at the annual Gauteng Province Research and Innovation Summit.

4.1.2 Stakeholder involvement and training

The Climate and Health Indicator Sub-Committee, chaired by Wits RHI, has convened a series of technical meetings to guide the implementation of selected indicators and determine appropriate reporting frequencies within existing systems. These meetings brought together representatives from key departments, research institutions, and implementing partners to review proposed indicators, assess data availability, and ensure alignment with national priorities. Discussions focused on distinguishing between short- and long-term indicators for monitoring, prioritising initial implementation related to heat, and establishing a baseline for tracking other extreme weather events in the future.

The sub-committee plays a critical role in ensuring that the implementation is feasible for routine monitoring, supports decision-making across the health and climate sectors, and generates learnings that can be shared with other countries.

4.1.3 Challenges

There are several key considerations when implementing the monitoring of indicators, particularly through routine systems and across multiple departments. Monitoring occurs at different levels (see Figure 5), and the purpose and use of data outputs can vary accordingly (WHO, 2024).

Figure 5. Potential levels of monitoring (WHO, 2024)

Note: This figure shows how a system transforms inputs into outcomes through structured processes. The bottom layer represents inputs, resources or foundational elements, while the middle layers show activities and intermediate outputs that progressively refine and shape these inputs. The top circle illustrates the final outcomes, outputs, or policies that result from the integrated effort of all underlying processes.

The initial experience has highlighted several challenges, including:

- Data is often aggregated rather than individual-level
- Data quality can be inconsistent
- Limited age disaggregation
- Health data is not captured in real time
- Weak cross-sectoral data sharing agreements
- Limited information on socio-economic status (SES)
- Adverse outcomes data is often not routinely collected.

There is limited evidence on attribution, which further complicates the implementation of monitoring selected climate-health indicators. In many cases, it is difficult to directly link specific health outcomes such as preterm births to climate-related exposures like heatwaves. This is due to multiple overlapping

determinants of health, such as SES, co-morbidities, and environmental factors, which can obscure causal pathways. The lack of robust, longitudinal data and local epidemiological studies weakens the ability to establish clear associations between climate hazards and health outcomes. As a result, it becomes challenging to justify the inclusion of certain indicators, determine appropriate thresholds for action, or advocate for policy responses based on the available evidence.

4.1.4 Discussion

The monitoring of climate-health indicators presents a unique set of challenges and opportunities for strengthening health system responsiveness to climate risks. While the Climate and Health Indicator Sub-Committee, chaired by Wits RHI, has made progress through a series of technical meetings to guide the selection and implementation of indicators, several operational and structural barriers remain.

The complexity of implementing indicators through routine health systems and across departments requires coordination, clarity of purpose, and alignment on data use across different levels of the system. Early experiences reveal limitations such as reliance on aggregate rather than individual-level data, variable data quality, lack of age and socio-economic disaggregation, delays in real-time reporting, and weak cross-sectoral data-sharing mechanisms.

There is limited evidence on attribution, which complicates efforts to establish direct links between climate exposures and health outcomes, thus making it difficult to define actionable thresholds or justify inclusion of certain indicators. The ongoing discussions have also underscored the importance of distinguishing between short- and long-term indicators, with heat-related indicators prioritised for initial implementation and serving as a baseline for tracking broader climate-related health impacts.

The indicator sub-committee's work is intended not only to strengthen national monitoring and inform evidence-based decision-making but also to generate insights that can guide indicator development and climate-health adaptation strategies in other LMIC contexts. As a next step, the process for selecting and refining short- and long-term indicators will be expedited to ensure timely implementation. Results will be compiled into quarterly reports and shared with the National Climate Change and Health Steering Committee to support coordinated action. In addition, the evidence generated through this process will help shape national research priorities and inform future planning. Key learnings will also be highlighted in the upcoming DHB report to promote broader dissemination and policy engagement.

4.2 Zimbabwe

Monitoring heat-related MNCH indicators in Zimbabwe is at an earlier stage. Efforts are now focused on building strong cross-sectoral coordination mechanisms and defining the indicators needed to inform effective policy and planning.

4.2.1 Recent developments

Following the indicators prioritisation process conducted by HIGH Horizons and national stakeholders in January 2024, stakeholders developed a list of indicators proposed for tracking. Before considering an indicator for tracking in Zimbabwe, there is a need for extensive stakeholder engagement across all involved sectors. Thus, the major recommendation from the workshop was to establish the Intersectoral Coordination Cluster on Climate, Environment, and Health, which will further the agenda for tracking.

Zimbabwe finally established the Zimbabwe Intersectoral Coordination Cluster on Climate, Environment, and Health (ZICC-EH) on July 1, 2025, after several engagements with various sectors, including government ministries. The ZICC-EH

consists of government sectors, civil society organisations, community leaders, UN agencies, and researchers.

4.2.2 Stakeholder involvement and training

Stakeholders participated in the consultative process to form the ZICC-EH and develop its terms of reference. All stakeholders from the government, UN agencies, researchers from CeSHHAR, community leaders, and civil society organisations provided their input for the terms of reference, reviewed them accordingly, and endorsed them at a launch meeting held on July 1, 2025.

4.2.3 Challenges

The lack of dedicated funding for engagements with stakeholders derailed progress in the formation of the ZICC-EH, ultimately delaying the tracking process. Additionally, the absence of a clear definition of a heatwave from a health perspective, since there only is a definition from a meteorological standpoint, poses a challenge in tracking MNCH outcomes influenced by heat.

4.2.4 Discussion

There is an urgent need to define indicators, especially temperature thresholds, to make informed decisions on indicators for tracking. A pilot project for tracking these indicators is recommended before nationally scaling the effort, allowing to refine the selected indicators. It is essential to work closely with other sectors, particularly the meteorological department and health information systems.

4.3 Consultations with national and global stakeholders

Noting that HIGH Horizons countries represent only two continents: Europe and Africa, the WHO Expert Group convened to discuss and select the heat-MNCH indicators expressed interest in data from a wider set of contexts. While resources to repeat the extensive consultations described in the previous sections were not

available, a plan was developed to consult a wider set of global and national stakeholders through qualitative interviews.

HIGH Horizons partner, the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM), developed a protocol which had an overall aim to engage country and global stakeholders in examining potential global guidance on indicators to monitor the impact of heat and climate on MNCH, examining their availability, feasibility, usability and appropriateness in the national or relevant context. Current countries where interviews have been conducted include Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, and Thailand (including a humanitarian context on Myanmar border). Interviewees are a convenience sample of United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), WHO, World Meteorological Organization (WMO), ministry of health, and relevant non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in each country, suggested by HIGH Horizons researchers. The interviews are being conducted face-to-face in each country or remote on Zoom. In addition, LSHTM aims to interview global and regional stakeholders from Europe (such as the European Commission, European Climate and Health Observatory, national authorities and selected countries, Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) countries, international NGOs such as Red Cross and Save the Children, DHIS2, members of WHO Advisory groups on global MNCH monitoring, e.g., MoNITOR and CHAT, and members of global networks, e.g. Health Data Collaborative (HDC) or Every Women Every Newborn Everywhere (EWENE). The generic interview topic guide is included in Annex: Interview Topic Guide (chapter 8), and the tool will be adjusted relevant to each context. Interviews and final reports will be completed by September 2025 and is complementing the HIGH Horizons work on indicator selection.

5 Future steps

5.1 At country level

On 15 and 16 December 2025, the University of Thessaly will host a country indicator workshop in Greece, jointly with the Greek National Public Health Organisation. Given the success of the country indicator workshops in South Africa and Zimbabwe, HIGH Horizons hopes to end the two-day workshop with a prioritisation of heat-health indicators for optimal tracking the effects of heat exposure on maternal, newborn and child health outcomes in Greece. The next (and last) annual report (deliverable D4.4) will report on the decisions taken in the workshop.

In South Africa, the Climate and Health Indicator Sub-Committee will continue refining short- and long-term MNCH heat-health indicators to ensure timely implementation. Indicator tracking results will be compiled in quarterly reports and shared with the National Climate Change and Health Steering Committee, while key lessons will also be featured in the upcoming District Health Barometer report to encourage national policy engagement. In Zimbabwe, the focus will be on operationalising the work of the newly established ZICC-EH. The ZICC-EH will therefore recommend a few key heat-health indicators for monitoring in one district and assess their feasibility before scaling up. Stakeholders will agree on a definition of a heatwave from a health standpoint, which will be incorporated into the weekly disease surveillance. This will help attribute MNCH outcomes to the noted episodes of heatwaves. The ZICC-EH will outline how to implement this, and this is on top of the agenda for the next ZICC-EH meeting scheduled for October 2025.

To further expand the geographic coverage of the HIGH Horizons country work in Europe and Africa, additional consultations through a series of qualitative interviews are being carried out, aiming to assess the feasibility, relevance, and

appropriateness of MNCH heat-health indicators in different settings, including Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, and Thailand, with consideration of humanitarian contexts such as the Myanmar border, as well as the European and global context. Interviews are being conducted with stakeholders from EU organisations such as the European Climate and Health Observatory, UN agencies, ministries of health, NGOs, and technical advisory bodies. The findings from these interviews will be available by September 2025 and will be shared in the next (and last) annual report.

5.2 At global level

At the global level, the WHO Expert Group, convened within the context of HIGH Horizons, will meet in late 2025 to select and prioritise heat-MNCH indicators, which will result in a joint WHO-UNICEF-UNFPA-WMO publication in 2026, comprising global and national indicators to monitor the impacts of heat on MNCH.

The challenge of the future work on indicator selection and application will be to identify a set of heat-MNCH indicators that are not only scientifically robust but also available, feasible, and usable across a wide range of contexts, while drawing together and synthesising the findings and experiences generated through the HIGH Horizons project to date. The selection of a final set of indicators will build on lessons learned from indicator selection and implementation in South Africa, Zimbabwe and Greece, insights from data analyses on the effects of heat exposure on perinatal health outcomes using birth registries or hospital data from multiple countries, findings from the systematic review updates and insights and recommendations from country stakeholder qualitative interviews.

Trade-offs will need to be recognised between scientific robustness and feasibility, ensuring that the selected indicators are both meaningful and implementable. Key challenges to address include the limited availability and quality of disaggregated

data, the difficulty of attributing health outcomes directly to heat exposure, weak cross-sectoral data-sharing mechanisms, inconsistent definitions of terms such as “heatwave”, capacity constraints within health information systems, gaps in local evidence to inform threshold-setting, and the need to build alignment and consensus among diverse stakeholders across sectors and countries.

The dissemination of heat-MNCH indicators is planned in 2026 in the joint WHO/UNICEF/UNFPA publication, but actions will be undertaken beforehand to gather feedback from stakeholders on the suggested list, potentially through inclusion in the next WHO MNCH Policy Survey if it is conducted and funding allows. Insights from this process will help ensure the indicators remain relevant and useful over time.

6 Conclusion

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the development and application of heat-related MNCH indicators at global and country level. First, it maps existing MNCH indicators against the WHO-HIGH Horizons conceptual framework, revealing gaps in validated indicators, especially for direct health impacts and vulnerability factors, with many indicators currently captured through research rather than routine health systems. Second, it examines national heat-health action plans, highlighting that although children and pregnant individuals are often recognised as vulnerable groups, few plans include detailed or age-disaggregated MNCH indicators specific to heat exposure. Third, the experience from country-level indicator application in South Africa and Zimbabwe is illustrated, such as progress in integrating MNCH heat-health indicators into national monitoring systems and fostering multisectoral collaboration, while also identifying persistent challenges such as inconsistent data quality, limited real-time reporting, and a need for clear health sector definitions of heatwaves.

In conclusion, while a lot of efforts have been made in the identification and application of potential indicators for MNCH, future HIGH Horizons work will focus on selecting a final set of indicators that is not only scientifically robust but also applicable across diverse country contexts, with the selection process informed by the lessons and evidence from country experiences such as those in South Africa, Zimbabwe, and the upcoming workshop in Greece. The final set of heat-MNCH indicators will be published in a joint WHO/UNICEF/UNFPA/WMO publication, also deliverable D6.4.

It will also be important to determine whether existing data collected through routine health information systems can be adapted to meet the criteria required for effective indicator monitoring, or whether certain indicators should be tracked separately from those already captured. Furthermore, additional research within and beyond the HIGH Horizons project is needed to guide countries on integrating MNCH considerations and relevant indicators into their national HHAPs, ensuring that vulnerable populations are systematically accounted for in preparedness and response strategies. Upcoming deliverables that will contribute to this effort include deliverable D4.4, the annual report on the application of MNCH indicators, and deliverable D5.1, the report on the performance and suitability of proposed indicators. Finally, more research is also required on attribution to establish direct links between climate exposures and health outcomes, strengthening the evidence base for targeted interventions. This is being addressed in deliverable D2.5, focusing on heat-health attribution.

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8 Annex: Interview Topic Guide

Indicators for monitoring heat impacts on maternal, newborn and child health (MNCH)

Key stakeholder interviews – Topic guide

This topic guide provides an indication of the kinds of questions that will be asked in the interview, but these can be somewhat flexible as required. Where appropriate and relevant, supplementary questions may be asked to seek further detail and/or clarification. For example, participants may be asked to provide an example, or to elaborate on a point that has been raised.

1. Roles and responsibilities:

- Can you tell me about your role and responsibilities, particularly in relation to maternal, newborn and child health (MNCH) and/or heat and climate change?
 - Organisation
 - Title/Role
 - Areas of work/expertise (check all that apply):
 - ♣ MNCH
 - ♣ Climate Change
 - ♣ Meteorology
 - ♣ Health Monitoring/Data Systems

2. Current priorities for MNCH and heat/climate change programming and adaptation in [Country or context]:

- Does your organisation have a programmatic focus on MNCH and heat and/or climate change? If so, what are your current priorities in this area?
- Does the organisation's strategy include adaptation and/or mitigation (facility carbon emission reduction) interventions needed to protect MNCH from extreme heat?
 - Probe: Strategies currently being implemented to address the impacts of heat on MNCH.

3. Integration of MNCH, heat & climate change monitoring in [Country or context]:

- Does the organisation currently monitor MNCH and/or heat and climate change health outcomes?
- Does the organisation support the Ministry of Health and other relevant ministries to monitor MNCH and/or heat and climate change outcomes?
- How often do you and/or does the Ministry or Department of Health

revise/update the indicators for your routine health monitoring information system?

- Do you work regularly with your local meteorologic colleagues (if health) or health (if climate/meteorology)?
 - If yes, please describe collaborations.
- Is health data currently being combined with climate/meteorologic data to examine heat and climate impacts on health outcomes?
 - Probe: If yes, which heat/climate data and health outcomes are included?
- What challenges exist in linking MNCH outcomes to heat exposure in [Country or context]?

4. Global partners are interested in better understanding the impact of extreme heat on MNCH outcomes, as recent studies have shown risks. Given your knowledge of (MNCH or heat/climate change), we wanted to hear your views on the proposed global indicators for monitoring heat impacts on women and children (MNCH) for the [Country or context]:

MNCH List – see list in Conceptual Framework for review – for those who ticked MNCH or Health Monitoring/Data Systems above

And/or

Heat/Climate Indicators – see attached list/Conceptual Framework for review – for those who ticked Meteorology or Climate above

If interviewee ticked across expertise you can ask them both sets.

[Interviewer to review list of attached indicators and ask about the following questions]:

- **Availability:** Are you currently collecting data on these indicators in [Country or context]?
 - How is this collected
 - ♣ **MNCH Data:** Health Facilities (paper or DHIS 2 or related HMIS), Routine Surveys (DHS, MICS, Facility, EmONC)?
 - If others, from which source?
 - ♣ **Heat Data:** Monitoring stations, satellite data?
 - If satellite data, from which source?
 - If others, from which source?
 - How regularly is this data above collected (e.g. daily, weekly, monthly, annual, intermittent)?
 - How would you describe its data quality?
- **Feasibility:** If not, how feasible would it be to collect data on these indicators as part of your routine monitoring in [Country or context]?
 - What are the potential barriers?

- **Appropriateness:** How appropriate do you consider these indicators to be for [Country or context]?
 - If no, please explain.
- **Usability:** If you have/had this data how would you plan to use it for policy and/or programming purposes to protect women and children from heat?
 - How user-friendly do you consider these indicators to be for the [Country or context]?
- **What other indicators would you suggest are appropriate for your [Country or context] not included in this potential list?**
 - Why do you suggest these indicators?

5. Future priorities:

- Thinking ahead, what do you consider as other key priorities to monitor for the future as it relates to heat and climate change impacts on (pregnant and postpartum?) women and children (MNCH)?
- In your view, what would help to bring about greater alignment between the MNCH and heat and climate adaptation and mitigation agendas in [Country or context]?

Is there anything else you'd like to add or share with me?